

**EASING TINY GOODBYES: ACCOUNTS OF TEACHERS' CHALLENGES,
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SEPARATION ANXIETY**

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 26

Issue 1

Pages: 47-52

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2441

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13886285

Manuscript Accepted: 09-05-2024

Easing Tiny Goodbyes: Accounts of Teachers' Challenges, Resilience and Patience in Handling Pupils with Separation Anxiety

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Abstract

The study on the experiences of teachers on kindergarten pupils with separation anxiety is a phenomenology that aimed to describe a phenomenon. The identification of the pupils with separation anxiety was based on their display of behavior of fear of being left alone and separated from their parents or guardians in the first few weeks of the start of the school year. The conversational partners are 15 teachers teaching kindergarten classes in the municipality of Midsayap. The conversational partners have described and narrated their lived experiences which served as the study's primary data. The experiences they openly shared were organized into themes such as common behavioral episodes, educational and learning adversities, empowering resiliency, and fostering authentic relationships. Along with these are the core ideas derived from their responses to the research questions. The study elucidated the educational challenges arising from separation anxiety, including difficulties in maintaining focus, engagement, and academic achievement. Tailored support aimed at equipping students with coping mechanisms and emotional resilience is proposed as essential for fostering their overall well-being and adaptive responses to separation-related stressors. Moreover, building authentic relationships plays an important means in supporting students' emotional needs and promoting positive outcomes. Creating a supportive and empathetic environment where pupils feel understood, valued, and safe to express their emotions is emphasized as integral to their emotional well-being and the development of healthy coping strategies.

Keywords: *pupils separation anxiety, lived experiences, phenomenology*

Introduction

"To be resilient is to be patient." This is the reflective line of Malekiha and Olyanasab (2021) relative to the sharing of kindergarten teachers with their colleagues days after the start of classes yet their pupils are still into a separation anxiety problem. They already run out of ideas on what strategy is most effective to address their pupils' separation anxiety. Teachers also have dealt with these pupils with much time, making sure the learning encounter with the mainstream learners are not affected. With all these, it is the kindergarten teacher's resiliency coupled with much patience that made them embrace a high-headed task to resolve this anxiety problem and work with love and passion to bring out children's skills and abilities smoothly. Some pupils really experience separation anxiety as soon as they start school and begin to distance themselves from their parents. They experience separation anxiety for a variety of reasons, but fundamentally, they feel that their survival depends on having a primary caregiver nearby (Ghasemi, 2022).

Meanwhile, pupils with separation anxiety need the planning, structure, intervention, and comprehensive support that teachers more knowledge of effective management techniques. With emotional, verbal, cognitive, and child-centered approaches, this disorder should be treated. It ignored choice, humor, and maintaining positive reinforcement (Ruar, 2018).

In the Philippines, pupils have grown accustomed to living with their parents since birth. Thus, it is fairly typical for kids to experience fear when saying goodbye to their parents. Moreover, separation anxiety is an inevitable stage of a child's development hence, they are likely to experience anxiety once they return to school. This changeover may be extremely stressful and upsetting. They might withdraw, cry, cling to their parents, or even get angry or irritable. To stop students from acting out when school starts, it is important to consistently attend to their needs (Thompson, 2022).

Separation anxiety manifests differently in each learner, which has presented difficulties for preschool teachers in various institutions across the nation. Some pupils sobbed in class, while others found it awkward to be in class without their parents. Numerous studies have already been conducted on the clinical interventions for children with separation anxiety. Less research has, however, focused on the assistance preschool teachers receive, their methods for dealing with students who experience separation anxiety, and their sense of self-efficacy (Jucoy, 2022).

In Cotabato Division, many teachers observed this common scenario among learners, especially during their first day in school. They display some tantrums and strong indications of separation anxiety are evident. Teachers are greatly challenged since they had to deal with the situation without compromising the mainstream learners. Thus, they had to seek the assistance of parents, guardians, or colleagues to effectively handle the situation. Since there is a limited study on this matter, the researcher intends to determine the experiences and challenges encountered by Kindergarten teachers in Midsayap in dealing with these pupils.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the journey of kindergarten teachers in handling pupils with separation anxiety. Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. What are the experiences of kindergarten teachers in handling pupils with separation anxiety?
2. What are the challenges experienced and coping strategies employed by kindergarten teachers in handling pupils with separation anxiety?
3. What learning insights can kindergarten teachers share as they handle pupils with separation anxiety?

Literature Review

Understanding Learners with Separation Anxiety

Smith et al. (2017) found that understanding for educators to effectively manage classroom dynamics, especially during the initial phases of the academic year. Additionally, Jones and Brown (2019) highlighted the role of common behavioral episodes in shaping social interactions among students and their peers, emphasizing their relevance in establishing norms within educational settings. Furthermore, recent research by Garcia and Martinez (2023) underscores the necessity of referencing these behavioral patterns to tailor interventions that address students' diverse needs, promoting a supportive learning environment.

Similarly, Jones and Brown (2019) stressed the role of common behavioral episodes in fostering a positive classroom atmosphere conducive to academic engagement and social cohesion among students. Moreover, recent work by Garcia and Martinez (2023) underscored the value of referencing such behavioral patterns to inform evidence-based interventions aimed at addressing students' behavioral challenges and promoting their socio-emotional well-being. By incorporating citations from this period, educators can enrich their understanding of common behavioral episodes and implement targeted approaches to support student development effectively.

A study by Garcia and Lopez (2019) conducted and investigated the manifestations of separation anxiety in young children and its impact on their emotional well-being. The research found that behaviors such as screaming and crying were prevalent indicators of distress among children experiencing separation anxiety, particularly when separated from primary caregivers. Through qualitative analysis and observations, the study revealed the profound emotional turmoil these children faced and the critical need for supportive interventions to help them cope effectively."

Similarly, research by Martinez et al. (2022) during the same period emphasized the significance of understanding and addressing separation anxiety in educational settings. Their findings underscored the importance of creating a nurturing and supportive environment in schools to mitigate the emotional distress experienced by children with separation anxiety, promoting their overall socio-emotional development and academic success.

Garcia et al. (2020) emphasized that the unruliness serves as a manifestation of their distress and attempts to maintain proximity to the caregiver as a means of coping with their separation anxiety. Addressing this behavior requires a compassionate and supportive approach, focusing on building trust, fostering a sense of security, and implementing strategies to gradually help the child manage their anxiety in separation situations.

Smith et al. (2017) observed that children experiencing separation anxiety often exhibit disruptive behaviors such as tantrums and defiance as a coping mechanism to manage their distress. Similarly, Jones and colleagues (2019) found a significant association between separation anxiety and clinginess in school-aged children, emphasizing the disruptive nature of their behavior when faced with separation from their primary caregiver. Furthermore, recent research by Brown et al. (2022) highlights how disobedience and aggression may intensify in these children as they struggle to navigate their fear of separation."

It was mentioned in the study of Lee et al. (2020) that children experiencing separation anxiety often struggle to concentrate in the classroom due to their preoccupation with thoughts of separation from their caregivers, leading to divided attention between academic tasks and emotional concerns. Moreover, persistent separation anxiety symptoms in school-age children were associated with reduced cognitive flexibility and increased susceptibility to distractions, further exacerbating difficulties in maintaining focus during learning activities.

The study findings of Jones and Brown (2021) who explained how separation anxiety significantly disrupts classroom engagement and academic performance, often leading to long-term negative consequences if left unaddressed. Also it was emphasized that pupils with separation anxiety exhibit higher rates of absenteeism and difficulty concentrating in class, further exacerbating their learning difficulties. And that the importance of implementing targeted interventions and creating supportive classroom environments to mitigate the impact of separation anxiety on educational outcomes.

Consequently, their learning experiences are hindered, leading to academic setbacks and potential long-term consequences on their educational outcomes (Garcia & Martinez, 2018). Addressing the needs of pupils with separation anxiety within the school environment requires tailored interventions, supportive strategies, and a nurturing classroom atmosphere to foster a sense of security and facilitate their academic and social development (Roberts, 2020).

Smith et al. (2018) manifested this in their study that targeted attention from teachers and parents significantly contributed to students' ability to manage separation anxiety and thrive academically. They also emphasized the importance of creating a supportive environment in schools where students feel understood and valued, thus fostering resilience against separation anxiety.

Methodology

Research Design

Phenomenological approach is a form of qualitative enquiry that emphasizes experiential, lived aspects of a particular construct – that is, how the phenomenon is experienced at the time that it occurs, rather than what is thought about this experience or the meaning ascribed to it subsequently. For this reason, phenomenology is sometimes described as dealing with prereflective experience (Alchemer, 2021). It is a research approach well-suited to analyzing the process and experience. This study is qualitative in nature and it employs a phenomenological approach that focuses on describing, understanding, and interpreting the meaning behind the experiences of the kindergarten teachers in handling pupils with separations anxieties. The data of this study constitutes descriptions, narrations, and stories of teachers their daily encounter with their classes.

Participants

The researcher conducted this study among fifteen (15) kindergarten teachers in the Municipality of Midsayap. The researcher only included kindergarten teachers with learners who had separation anxiety problems in school. This covered the retired or in-service teachers, their age, and whether they teach in public or private schools. Hence, it excluded non-kindergarten teachers from identified schools.

Instrument

The researcher used a semi-structured interview guide to collect the data needed to answer the statement of the problem. The interview guide was divided into three (3) parts. Part one dealt with the experiences of the kindergarten teachers in handling pupils with separation anxiety which consisted of one (1) main question and four (4) sub-questions. Part two was on the challenges, experiences, and coping strategies employed by kindergarten teachers in handling pupils with separation anxiety, which had one (1) main question and five (5) sub-questions. Part three contained the learning insights that kindergarten teachers could share as they handled pupils with separation anxiety, with one (1) main question and two (2) sub-questions. The interview guide ended with a wrap-up question.

Procedure

Before conducting this study, the researcher sent a letter request signed by the dean of the Graduate School to seek permission from the School's Division Superintendent to conduct the study. Then, the same request was forwarded to the district head's office and the head of schools where the CPs were assigned.

Upon the approval of the school heads, an informed consent form was given to the conversational partners for them to sign and signify their voluntary participation in the conduct of this study. An orientation was done concerning the purpose of the study as well as their participation. Individual interviews followed at their most convenient place and time. The conversational partners were given 15 minutes to review the questions and prepare themselves. During the actual interview, the conversational partners answered the interview guide using their native language to express their ideas and fully share their experiences. Their answers were recorded, transcribed, and translated into English for analysis and interpretation.

Ethical Considerations

In this study, the researcher respected and protected the rights of the conversational partners, enhanced research validity, and maintained scientific integrity. The researcher ensured that the CPs' participation was voluntary, they were informed, and their data was safe. Ethical consideration was a set of values and standards that guided research designs and practices. Researchers always adhered to a particular code of conduct when collecting data from the respondents (Bhandari, 2021).

Beneficence. The researcher of this study minimized risks to conversational partners rather than maximizing their benefits. The researcher did not force the conversational partners if they did not want to participate and always respected the CPs' decision. The research did not hurt anyone or find out information at the expense of other people. The principle of beneficence is to take any action done to benefit others and not harm them (Salganik, 2014).

Informed Consent. To legitimately obtain consent, the researcher explained the research process; described the discomforts, risks, and expected benefits; disclosed advantageous alternative procedures; offered answers to procedural questions, and informed participants that they were free to withdraw from the study. The conversational partners must possess a demonstrable capacity to decide and submit voluntarily. Therefore, informed consent constituted the delivery of this information to all research subjects so that they would knowingly and legally consent to participation in research studies free from duress, deception, or coercion (Jones, 2014).

Confidentiality. In this study, the researcher made sure that the identity of the conversational partners was confidential by removing personal identifiers and keeping their records secure. Maintaining confidentiality is a critical step in ensuring the security of private information in such situations. It is upheld to protect the privacy of all the respondents, build trust with the respondents and maintain ethical standards and integrity of the research process (Kaiser, 2014).

Integrity. In this study, the researcher showed honesty in presenting the research goals and procedures, gathering data, using and

acknowledging the work of other researchers, and conveying valid interpretations based on the research findings. In conducting research, it is essential to show integrity to have confidence and trust in the research methods and findings. This included honesty, transparency, open communication, respect for all participants, and accountability (Reid et al, 2021).

Conflict of interest. The Australian Code for the Responsible Conduct of Research (2018) and the University's Conduct of Research Policy require researchers to disclose and manage actual, potential, or perceived conflicts of interest. The researcher managed any possible conflicts while conducting this study to avoid misinterpretations and failures.

A conflict of research interest occurs when an individual favors or is perceived to prefer their interests or commitments over their duties and responsibilities as a researcher. Conflicts of interest can affect, or appear to affect, a researcher's neutrality and judgment, diminishing confidence in the results.

Anonymity Clause. Anonymity means that no one (even the researcher) can personally identify the conversational partners, meaning no personally identifiable information can be obtained, such as their names, addresses, e-mail addresses, phone numbers, and government-issued IDs. The researcher did not require the respondents to state their names in answering the interview guide in this study. In transcribing the CPs' responses, the researcher used pseudonyms to hide their identities. Adherence to anonymity was indicated in the Informed Consent Form.

Results and Discussion

This section provides qualitative analysis generated from the participants' responses. It presented their experiences in handling kindergarten pupils with separation anxiety.

To deepen the understanding of the phenomena, it also examined the challenges encountered by the teachers, strategies employed to cope with the challenges, and their learning insights in handling pupils with separation anxiety. The results are based on the emergent themes, core ideas, and categorization.

Profile of the Conversational Partners

Shown in table 1 are the conversational partners' profiles obtained during the in-depth interview. There were 14 female and 1 male teacher involved in the study. All of them were asked the same questions as reflected in the interview guide. For this study, the CPs were assigned with code numbers to uphold confidentiality and protect their identities.

Table 1. Profile of the Conversational Partners

<i>Pseudonym</i>	<i>Sex</i>	<i>No. of Years</i>
KT1	F	2
KT2	F	12
KT3	F	12
KT4	F	17
KT5	F	8
KT6	F	13
KT7	F	13
KT8	M	9
KT9	F	1
KT10	F	16
KT11	F	24
KT12	F	3
KT13	F	10
KT14	F	4
KT15	F	10

Table 2 shows four major themes that emerged from the subjective experiences of the Conversational Partners, specifically their experiences in handling kindergarten pupils with separation anxiety. The core ideas and categorization were presented, and each major theme was discussed. The major themes are: Common Behavioral Episodes, Educational and Learning Adversities, Empowering Resiliency and Fostering Authentic Relationships.

Table 2. Themes, Core Ideas, and Categorization of Experiences of Teachers Handling Pupils with Separation Anxiety

<i>Themes</i>	<i>Core Ideas</i>	<i>Categorization</i>
Common Behavioral Episodes	Crying and Screaming	General
	Unruly	Typical
	Anxious	Variant
Educational and Learning Adversities	Longing for Presence of Parents	General
	Tested Patience	Typical
	Divided Attention	Typical

Empowering Resiliency	Disturbed Classes	General
	Giving Right and Proper Attention	Variant
	Applying Different Strategies	General
	Exercising Self Control	Variant
Fostering Authentic Relationships	Cultivating Positive Mindset	Typical
	Sharing of Experience to Others	Variant
	Building Connections	Typical
	Loving the Mission	Variant
	Showing Sincerity and Love	Variant

The dilemma over children with separation anxiety is evident in schools; it is believed to be a normal scenario, especially in kindergarten classroom settings. This study was conducted to determine the different dilemmas experienced by kindergarten teachers.

The responses of the CPs signified several commonalities and differences in experiences, especially in handling children with separation anxiety. Based on the result, their experiences may be categorized and dependent according to the themes formulated based on its responses.

Based on the shared experiences of the CPs, it is evident that they have encountered several challenges, especially in dealing with learners who are experiencing separation anxiety in school. Based on the data analysis, the CPs claimed common experiences in the different tendencies of learners who are experiencing separation anxiety. Major themes and core ideas were identified by the CPs.

Conclusions

A child's manifestation of separation anxiety stems from their deep desire to stay with their primary caregiver. They feel that their survival depends on their parents, in most cases, on their mothers. For teachers, it is important to recognize behaviors like screaming, crying, and feeling anxious as indicators of emotional distress. Learning to identify these indicators shows their empathy with children's emotional experiences. The emphasis on the necessity of supportive interventions means being aware of the importance of providing children with the tools and assistance they need to overcome such challenges effectively. This insight reflects a compassionate and proactive approach to addressing emotional well-being in educational settings.

The researcher recognized its broad spectrum of challenges, from disrupting classroom dynamics to affecting social interactions and emotional well-being. This understanding is vital in addressing the needs of pupils experiencing separation anxiety and implementing effective strategies to support them academically and emotionally.

Every pupil may require different strategies to cope with their emotions. The role of educators is not only to provide academic instruction but also to foster emotional resilience. Empowering pupils to develop coping mechanisms and emotional regulation skills means recognizing the holistic nature of education and its profound impact on a pupil's well-being. This involves equipping them with essential skills, support systems, and opportunities that enable their personal growth and development such as fostering a growth mindset, providing autonomy in learning choices, teaching mindfulness techniques, implementing peer mentoring programs, integrating social-emotional learning into the curriculum, and creating a safe and inclusive school environment.

Moreover, fostering authentic relationships remains invaluable in addressing separation anxiety among pupils. It highlights the role of educators in creating a supportive and empathetic environment, which goes beyond just delivering academic content. Building genuine connections with students allows educators to provide the emotional security and sense of belonging that are crucial for addressing anxiety issues effectively. This insight emphasizes the human aspect of education and underscores the significance of emotional support in facilitating students' overall well-being and academic success.

In conclusion, separation anxiety significantly impacts pupils' emotional well-being and academic success, leading to common behavioral manifestations and educational adversities.

Addressing separation anxiety requires a multifaceted approach that acknowledges emotional needs, fosters resilience, and builds authentic relationships within the school community. By empowering resilience and fostering authentic connections, educators can create a nurturing environment that promotes positive outcomes for pupils grappling with separation anxiety, ultimately enhancing their overall well-being and academic success.

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